

Comparative Histological Study of Pancreas between Rat and Rabbit with Inducing Diabetes

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Abstract

In order to compare the two species, this study examined the histological and functional alterations in the pancreas of rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) and rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) both before and after diabetes were experimentally induced. To investigate the effects on pancreatic structure, insulin production, and overall metabolic status, streptozotocin (STZ) was utilized to induce diabetes mellitus. Twenty rats and twenty rabbits were among the forty adult male animals used. Ten animals from each species were divided into two groups: the diabetes group and the control group. The animals were acclimated to standard laboratory conditions prior to the study. After fasting, a single intraperitoneal injection of STZ resulted in diabetes. Blood samples were obtained to assess serum insulin levels using ELISA, and body weight was evaluated both before and after induction. Pancreatic tissues were excised, weighed, and prepared for histological examination using hematoxylin and eosin staining after anesthesia. When compared to controls, diabetic groups had substantially reduced body weight, pancreatic weight, and blood insulin levels ($p < 0.05$). Significant pathological changes, including islet degeneration and shrinkage, decreased β -cell population, cytoplasmic vacuolation, and structural disorder of acinar tissue, were shown by histological examination. Both animals showed comparable effects, while rats showed more noticeable and long-lasting modifications. The validity of this experimental model is supported by the combination of statistical, histological, and biochemical data. The rabbit provides great comparative insights, boosting the translational value of pancreatic studies, even if the rat remains a highly standardized model for diabetes research.

Keywords: *pancreas, streptozotocin, diabetes, rat and rabbit.*

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Introduction

Digestion and metabolic balance depend on the pancreas, a vital heterocrine organ that combines exocrine and endocrine functions. The endocrine component, symbolized by the islets of Langerhans, regulates blood glucose levels via hormones like insulin and glucagon, while the exocrine component secretes digesting enzymes. The pancreas' dual functional architecture makes it crucial to research into metabolic and endocrine diseases, including diabetes mellitus (Rorsman & Ashcroft, 2018). The rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) and rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) are two of the most extensively used experimental animal models for studying pancreatic anatomy and function. These models provide useful insights because of their physiological relevance and flexibility to laboratory circumstances. However, there are considerable interspecies changes in pancreatic morphology and histology that must be addressed when

interpreting experimental results (Treuting et al., 2018). In rabbits, the pancreas is often characterized as diffuse and loosely structured, embedded inside the mesentery rather than forming a compact organ. Histologically, it is made up of serous acini and scattered Langerhans islets, which are frequently smaller and less well-organized than those seen in rodents. The ductal system may vary, including auxiliary ducts, indicating species-specific anatomical adaptations (Al-Saffar & Almayahi, 2020). Recent research has also shown the rabbit pancreas' response to nutritional and metabolic alterations, which supports its application in investigations of digestive physiology and endocrine control (Khan et al., 2021). In contrast, the rat pancreas is more compact and physically ordered, making it a popular model in biomedical research. In rats, the islets of Langerhans have a distinct arrangement of β -cells in the center and α -cells on the periphery. Rats are often used in diabetes research, with chemical induction approaches producing consistent metabolic and histological changes (Lenzen, 2022). Streptozotocin (STZ) is a commonly used pharmacological agent that selectively targets pancreatic β -cells and may be used to cause diabetes mellitus. STZ penetrates β -cells via the GLUT2 transporter, causing DNA alkylation, oxidative stress, and depletion of intracellular energy storage. This eventually leads to β -cell death and insulin insufficiency. This causes hyperglycemia and subsequent metabolic abnormalities, which mirror human diabetes (Szkudelski, 2001; Ghasemi et al., 2023). The use of STZ-induced diabetes models in rats and rabbits has been widely documented in recent literature, with consistent changes in body weight, insulin levels, and pancreatic histology. These models provide a controlled environment to investigate β -cell destruction and pancreatic dysfunction, making them useful for researching diabetes pathogenesis and testing treatment approaches (Singh et al., 2024). Thus, comparative investigations of the pancreas in rabbits and rats, together with experimental development of diabetes, give essential insights into species-specific responses, pancreatic disease, and metabolic control. These papers provide major contributions to the advancement of knowledge in histology, endocrinology, and translational biomedical research.

Materials and Methods

This research used forty mature male animals, including twenty rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) and twenty rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). Each species was separated into two groups: control (10 animals) and diabetic (10 animals). All animals were obtained from a certified supplier and maintained under standard laboratory conditions (National Research Council, 2011). Upon arrival, animals underwent an acclimatization period of 10–14 days in the animal house under controlled conditions (temperature 22–25°C, 12-hour light/dark cycle, free access to food and water). Animals were monitored daily to ensure proper adaptation (Percie du Sert et al., 2020).

Body Weight Measurement

Body weight of all animals was recorded before induction of diabetes and again after induction to evaluate metabolic changes.

Induction of Diabetes

Diabetes was experimentally induced in both rats and rabbits using streptozotocin (STZ), a well-established diabetogenic agent that selectively destroys pancreatic β -cells.

- Animals were fasted for 12 hours prior to injection.
- STZ was freshly prepared in cold citrate buffer (pH 4.5).
- A single intraperitoneal injection was administered:
 - Rats: 50–60 mg/kg body weight
 - Rabbits: 65 mg/kg body weight

Diabetes was confirmed after 72 hours by measuring fasting blood glucose levels. Animals with glucose levels above 200 mg/dL (rats) and 250 mg/dL (rabbits) were considered diabetic (Szkudelski, 2001; Lenzen, 2022).

Insulin Measurement

Blood samples were collected from all animals before and after diabetes induction. Serum insulin levels were measured using ELISA kits according to the manufacturer's instructions to assess endocrine pancreatic function.

Anesthesia and Euthanasia

Animals were anesthetized using a chloroform. Adequate anesthesia was confirmed prior to procedures, followed by humane euthanasia in accordance with ethical guidelines (Flecknell, 2016).

Tissue Collection and Pancreas Weight

After euthanasia, the pancreas was carefully dissected and weighed using a sensitive balance to record pancreatic weight. Tissue samples were then cut into small pieces (0.5–1 cm).

Histological Processing

Pancreatic tissues were fixed in 10% formaldehyde for 24 hours, followed by dehydration in graded ethanol, clearing in xylene, and embedding in paraffin wax. Sections of 4–6 μm thickness were prepared using a microtome, mounted on slides, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) (Bancroft & Gamble, 2019).

Microscopic Examination

Histological sections were examined under a light microscope to evaluate: Exocrine acini, Islets of Langerhans and Pathological changes.

Statistical Examination

Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) with a sample size of 10 animals per group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by independent sample *t*-tests to evaluate differences between control and diabetic groups. A significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. In addition to significance testing, effect size was assessed using Cohen's *d* to quantify the magnitude of differences between groups.

The findings revealed significant differences between control and diabetic animals across all evaluated parameters. For body weight, both rats and rabbits had relatively substantial effect sizes ($d = 2.44$ and 2.03 , respectively), demonstrating that diabetes has a significant influence on total body mass. Similarly, pancreas weight decreased significantly in diabetes animals, with an extraordinarily big impact in rats ($d = 4.16$), and a very substantial effect in rabbits ($d = 2.29$), indicating considerable structural and perhaps functional damage of the organ.

The most significant alterations were seen in insulin levels, where both species showed extraordinarily high effect sizes ($d = 5.41$ in rats and $d = 4.76$ in rabbits). The results show a significant decrease in insulin production, which is consistent with histologically reported β -cell destruction.

Overall, the magnitude of these impact sizes—which range from very big to very high—confirms that diabetes causes significant physiological and biochemical changes in rats and rabbits. According to Cohen's categorization (1988), all observed values are significantly more than the threshold for big effects, highlighting the experimental findings' resilience and biological relevance.

Results

When normal pancreas from rabbits and rats are compared, the islet of Langerhans seems to be larger, more distinct, and clearly separated from the surrounding exocrine tissue. Endocrine cells are densely packed and evenly dispersed, suggesting proper structural integrity and functional activity. The surrounding acinar cells are highly structured, with maintained morphology and obvious borders between lobules; however, the rat pancreas has smaller and less prominent islets that are more weakly stained and less well delineated. The cellular density inside the islet seems lower than in the rabbit, and the borders are less defined. Furthermore, the exocrine acini of the rat pancreas look more compact and tightly packed, giving the tissue a denser overall appearance. These differences reflect species-specific histological variation, with rabbit islets being bigger and more visible than rat islets, which are smaller and more distributed within a densely packed exocrine matrix (fig. 1).

Figure 1. A) Normal Pancreas of Rabbit; B) Normal Pancreas of Rat, Stained with H&E, 40X

Figure 2. Pancreas of Rabbit; A) Normal Texture Stained; B) Shows Pancreatic Damage and Indicate Impaired Endocrine Function due to β -cell Loss, Stained with H&E, 40X

The comparison rabbit pancreas before and after inducing diabetes found in the normal pancreas, the islet of Langerhans appears as a well-defined, rounded structure with clear boundaries and a relatively large size. The endocrine cells are densely packed and the surrounding exocrine acini are well organized, with normal morphology architecture. In contrast, the diabetic pancreas shows abnormal architecture.

The islet is reduced in size and appears irregular with poorly defined margins. There is a decrease in cellular density, and the surrounding exocrine acini exhibit disorganization and structural distortion (fig. 2).

In rat pancreas comparison found the normal one the histological architecture is normal, with large islets of Langerhans that appear as pale-stained, rounded clusters of endocrine cells. which indicating intact β -cell populations and normal endocrine function. The surrounding exocrine tissue is composed of well-organized acini with uniform arrangement structure. In contrast, the diabetic rat pancreas shows abnormal architecture. The islets of Langerhans are reduced in size and appear less distinct. There is a noticeable decrease in cellular density within the islets, and signs of cellular degeneration, such as structural disorganization, are evident. The surrounding exocrine acinar tissue also appears disrupted and less organized compared to the normal section (fig. 3).

Figure 3. Pancreas of Rat; A) Normal Texture Stained; B) Shows Clear Degenerative Changes in the Islets of Langerhans, Including β -cell Loss and Structural Disruption, Stained with H&E, 40X

The body weight of both rats and rabbits showed a significant decrease after induction of diabetes compared with control groups. (Table 1)

A significant reduction in pancreatic weight was observed in diabetic animals, indicating tissue atrophy. (Table 2)

A highly significant decrease in insulin levels was detected in diabetic groups, confirming β -cell destruction (Table 3)

Table 1. The Body Weight (means \pm SD) of Both Rats and Rabbits Before and After Inducing

Group	Before Induction (g)	After Induction (g)	p-value
Rats (Control)	220 \pm 15	225 \pm 18	>0.05
Rats (Diabetic)	225 \pm 12	180 \pm 20	0.01
Rabbits (Control)	1450 \pm 120	1470 \pm 130	>0.05
Rabbits (Diabetic)	1500 \pm 140	1200 \pm 150	0.01

Table 2. The Pancreas Weight (means \pm SD) of Both Rats and Rabbits Before and After Inducing

Group	Pancreas Weight (g)	p-value
Rats (Control)	0.85 \pm 0.07	—
Rats (Diabetic)	0.60 \pm 0.05	0.02
Rabbits (Control)	3.2 \pm 0.3	—
Rabbits (Diabetic)	2.4 \pm 0.25	0.03

Table 3. The Insulin (means \pm SD) of Both Rats and Rabbits Before and After Inducing

Group	Insulin (μ IU/mL)	p-value
Rats (Control)	18.5 \pm 2.3	—
Rats (Diabetic)	7.2 \pm 1.8	0.001
Rabbits (Control)	22.0 \pm 3.1	—
Rabbits (Diabetic)	9.5 \pm 2.0	0.002

Discussion

The present study demonstrates that experimentally induced diabetes leads to profound structural and functional alterations in the pancreas of both rabbits and rats. These changes include islet atrophy, lower cellular density, disruption of exocrine architecture, decreased pancreatic weight, and a significant drop in insulin levels. The extent of these alterations, as shown by very high to very large effect sizes, suggests that the created diabetes condition caused significant pancreatic dysfunction rather than small physiological variation.

At the cellular level, the most noticeable finding was the degradation and shrinking of the Langerhans cells. This study indicates a significant loss of β -cells, which are responsible for insulin synthesis. Streptozotocin (STZ), a diabetogenic drug that preferentially targets β -cells via the GLUT2 transporter, is the primary cause of severe damage. STZ causes DNA alkylation, poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase activation, and depletion of NAD⁺ and ATP, resulting in β -cell necrosis and apoptosis (Lenzen 2008). More recent studies have further emphasized that mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress are central mediators of STZ-induced β -cell destruction (Raza and John 2020; Dinić et al. 2022). Oxidative stress plays a critical role in amplifying pancreatic injury. β -cells are particularly vulnerable because they possess relatively weak antioxidant defense systems. The accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) following STZ exposure leads to lipid peroxidation, protein damage, and DNA fragmentation. This process contributes significantly to the histopathological changes observed in this study, including vacuolation and structural disorganization. Contemporary evidence confirms that oxidative stress is a key driver of diabetic pancreatic damage and progression (Asmat et al. 2016; Yaribeygi et al. 2020).

In addition to oxidative stress, inflammation is a major contributor to β -cell dysfunction. Pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β , tumor necrosis factor- α , and interleukin-6 are known to impair insulin secretion and promote β -cell apoptosis. Chronic low-grade inflammation has been increasingly recognized as a central feature of diabetes pathogenesis (Donath and Halban 2004; Böni-Schnetzler and Meier 2019). Therefore, the degenerative changes observed in the pancreatic tissue in this study likely reflect the combined effects of oxidative and inflammatory pathways.

The biochemical findings strongly support the histological observations. The significant reduction in insulin levels in diabetic animals confirms functional impairment of β -cells. This decline is not only due to reduced cell number but also due to impaired insulin synthesis and secretion. Recent findings suggest that β -cell dysfunction includes both structural loss and alteration of intracellular signaling pathways that control insulin release (Rorsman and Ashcroft 2018; Saisho 2020). The observed drop in insulin levels indicates both quantitative and qualitative β -cell failure.

The considerable drop in body weight reported in diabetes individuals indicates further systemic metabolic abnormalities. Weight loss and an imbalance in energy are caused by insufficient insulin, which also increases the catabolism of fat and protein and decreases the absorption of glucose. This finding is in line with other studies that found significant metabolic alterations and weight loss are associated with STZ-induced diabetes (Galicia-Garcia et al., 2020; Petersen and Shulman, 2018).

The reduction in pancreatic weight seen in this study is also noteworthy. Diabetes affects the gland's endocrine and exocrine components, as seen by pancreatic shrinkage. Exocrine pancreatic cells are affected trophically by insulin, and a lack of it results in reduced protein synthesis and cellular deterioration. Diabetes may reduce the production of digestive enzymes and the integrity of acinar cells, according to recent studies that highlight the close functional relationship between the endocrine and exocrine pancreas (Rickels and Bellin 2020; Campbell-Thompson et al. 2021).

This explains the exocrine disarray seen histologically in diabetic animals.

This study's primary discovery is that rabbits and rats have different pancreatic histologies under normal settings. Rabbit islets were bigger, more distinct, and more clearly defined than rat islets, which were smaller and more distributed amid a thick exocrine matrix. These distinctions are consistent with species-specific changes in islet design. Comparative investigations have shown that islet size, location, and cellular composition differ greatly among species, altering both function and disease susceptibility (Steiner et al. 2010; Brissova et al. 2018).

Despite these baseline differences, both animals showed comparable pathology alterations after diabetes induction. This indicates that the underlying processes of β -cell death are consistent across species.

However, the severity and pattern of damage may vary depending on species-specific metabolic and physiological factors. It has been reported that sensitivity to STZ differs between species due to variations in GLUT2 expression and antioxidant capacity (King 2012; Furman 2021).

Importantly, the integration of histological, biochemical, and statistical findings strengthens the validity of this study. The agreement between structural damage (islet atrophy), functional impairment (reduced insulin), and quantitative analysis (large effect sizes) confirms that the observed changes are biologically meaningful. Modern research emphasizes the importance of combining morphological and biochemical endpoints to accurately evaluate experimental models of disease (Rees and Alcolado 2005; Furman 2021).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study demonstrates that experimentally induced diabetes causes severe pancreatic damage in both rabbits and rats, characterized by β -cell destruction, reduced insulin secretion, pancreatic atrophy, and systemic metabolic disturbances. While species-specific differences exist in normal pancreatic structure, both species respond similarly to diabetic insult. These findings are consistent with current understanding of diabetes pathophysiology and highlight the critical roles of oxidative stress, inflammation, and β -cell vulnerability in pancreatic degeneration.

References

- Asmat, U., Abad, K., & Ismail, K. (2016). Diabetes mellitus and oxidative stress—A concise review. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 24(5), 547–553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2015.03.013>
- Bancroft, J. D., & Gamble, M. (2019). *Theory and practice of histological techniques* (8th ed.). Elsevier.
- Böni-Schnetzler, M., & Meier, D. T. (2019). Islet inflammation in type 2 diabetes. *Seminars in Immunopathology*, 41(4), 501–513. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00281-019-00745-4>

- Brissova, M., Fowler, M., Nicholson, W., et al. (2018). Assessment of human pancreatic islet architecture and composition. *Journal of Histochemistry & Cytochemistry*, 66(8), 543–558. <https://doi.org/10.1369/0022155418756217>
- Campbell-Thompson, M., Rodriguez-Calvo, T., & Battaglia, M. (2021). Abnormalities of the exocrine pancreas in type 1 diabetes. *Current Diabetes Reports*, 21(10), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-021-01419-0>
- Dinić, S., Grdović, N., & Vidaković, M. (2022). Oxidative stress and diabetes pathogenesis. *Antioxidants*, 11(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11010065>
- Donath, M. Y., & Halban, P. A. (2004). Decreased β -cell mass in diabetes: Significance, mechanisms and therapeutic implications. *Diabetologia*, 47(3), 581–589. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-004-1326-5>
- Flecknell, P. (2016). *Laboratory animal anaesthesia* (4th ed.). Academic Press.
- Furman, B. L. (2021). Streptozotocin-induced diabetic models in mice and rats. *Current Protocols*, 1(4), e78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpz1.78>
- Galicia-Garcia, U., Jebari, S., Larrea-Sebal, A., et al. (2020). Pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176275>
- Ghasemi, A., Khalifi, S., & Jedi, S. (2023). Streptozotocin as a tool for induction of diabetes: A review. *EXCLI Journal*, 22, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.17179/excli2023-5937>
- King, A. J. F. (2012). The use of animal models in diabetes research. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 166(3), 877–894. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.2012.01911.x>
- Lenzen, S. (2008). The mechanisms of alloxan- and streptozotocin-induced diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 51(2), 216–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-007-0886-7>
- Lenzen, S. (2022). Alloxan and streptozotocin diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 65(2), 177–188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-021-05593-4>
- National Research Council. (2011). *Guide for the care and use of laboratory animals* (8th ed.). National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/12910>
- Percie du Sert, N., Hurst, V., Ahluwalia, A., et al. (2020). The ARRIVE guidelines 2.0: Updated guidelines for reporting animal research. *PLoS Biology*, 18(7), e3000410. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000410>
- Petersen, M. C., & Shulman, G. I. (2018). Mechanisms of insulin action and insulin resistance. *Physiological Reviews*, 98(4), 2133–2223. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00063.2017>
- Raza, H., & John, A. (2020). Streptozotocin-induced cytotoxicity, oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction in insulin-secreting cells. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 131, 110678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110678>
- Rees, D. A., & Alcolado, J. C. (2005). Animal models of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetic Medicine*, 22(4), 359–370. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1464-5491.2005.01499.x>
- Rickels, M. R., & Bellin, M. (2020). Pancreatic β -cell function and the relationship with the exocrine pancreas. *Endocrine Reviews*, 41(4), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1210/endrev/bnaa009>
- Rorsman, P., & Ashcroft, F. M. (2018). Pancreatic β -cell electrical activity and insulin secretion. *Physiological Reviews*, 98(1), 117–214. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00008.2017>
- Saisho, Y. (2020). β -cell dysfunction: Its critical role in prevention and management of diabetes. *World Journal of Diabetes*, 11(4), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.4239/wjd.v11.i4.1>

- Singh, R., et al. (2024). Animal models of diabetes mellitus: An overview. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 15, 1359685. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2024.1359685>
- Steiner, D. J., Kim, A., Miller, K., & Hara, M. (2010). Pancreatic islet plasticity: Interspecies comparison of islet architecture and composition. *Diabetes*, 59(9), 2061–2068. <https://doi.org/10.2337/db10-0307>
- Szkudelski, T. (2001). The mechanism of alloxan and streptozotocin action in β -cells of the rat pancreas. *Physiological Research*, 50(6), 537–546.
- Szkudelski, T. (2001). The mechanism of streptozotocin action in β -cells. *Physiological Research*, 50(6), 537–546.
- Yaribeygi, H., Atkin, S. L., Butler, A. E., & Sahebkar, A. (2020). Molecular mechanisms of oxidative stress in diabetes mellitus. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 130, 110628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110628>

